

Fusing Regional and Global Land Cover Maps: An Application for Ecosystem Modeling Across High Latitudes

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Land cover is a critical dataset for studying permafrost dynamics, carbon cycling, ecosystem resilience, and climate feedbacks in high-latitude environments. However, global land cover products often fail to capture the spatial heterogeneity and ecological detail required for Arctic-Boreal applications.

This circumpolar 1-km land cover map integrates global (ESA-CCI-LC) and regional datasets using a machine learning-based fusion approach to generate 35 detailed land cover classes, including forest, shrubland, and wetland types. The map ensures thematic richness and consistency across the Arctic-Boreal zone, supporting improved climate modeling and ecological analysis. Further methodological details can be found in the associated publication.

Figure 1. The overview of the hybrid land cover product
Class Class Name

- 6 Poplar Forest
- 7 Oak Forest
- 10 Other Pine Forest

- 11 Fir Forest
- 12 Aspen Forest
- 13 Hemlock Forest
- 14 Spruce Forest
- 15 White Spruce Forest
- 16 Black Spruce Forest
- 17 Mixed Forest
- 18 Larch (Tamarack) Forest
- 19 Birch Forest
- 20 Scots Pine Forest
- 21 Jack Pine Forest
- 22 Cedar Forest
- 23 Maple Forest
- 24 Siberian Pine Forest
- 25 Linden Forest
- 26 Cedar Elfin Wood Forest
- 30 Alpine Shrubland
- 31 Riparian Shrubland
- 32 Other Shrubland
- 33 Herbaceous
- 35 Sparsely Vegetated
- 50 Bog
- 51 Fen
- 52 Marsh
- 60 Erect-shrub tundra
- 61 Prostrate-shrub tundra
- 62 Shrub tundra
- 63 Graminoid tundra
- 64 Wet-sedge tundra
- 65 Barren tundra
- 70 Developed
- 96 Bare, Rock
- 97 Other
- 98 Water
- 99 Snow/Ice

Projection information:

Spatial reference: WGS 1984 NSIDC EASE-Grid 2.0 North
Linear unit: Meter
Angular unit: Degree
False easting: 0

False northing: 0
Central meridian: 0
Latitude_of_origin:
90